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Effect of royal jelly on *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* based on total DNA, RNA and protein levels

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Abstract

Royal jelly is a highly nutritious secretion produced by the hypopharyngeal and mandibular glands of young worker honeybees (*Apis mellifera*). However, limited studies have investigated the chemical and biological properties of royal jelly produced at different honey types. This study evaluated six types of royal jelly (RJ) produced during the flowering of four crops (Cotton, clover, citrus, and eucalyptus), as well as those produced by colonies fed on a sugar solution supplemented with black seed extract and mint leaves during periods when flowering crops were not available, by assessing their chemical composition, sugar, fatty acids and amino acid profile/mg/100 mg (es, and antibacterial activity in vitro. Ash content of royal jelly varied from 0.45 m (RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with Menthol) to 1.40 mg/100 mg (RJ produced during the flowering of cotton). The pH values ranged between 3.40 (RJ produced during the flowering of clover and citrus) and 4.70 (RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with black sativa). Crude protein levels ranged from 11.10 (RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with menthol) to 13.40 mg/100 mg (RJ produced during the flowering of Citrus). Total lipid content varied between 8.0 (RJ produced during the flowering of clover) and 10.4 mg/100 mg (RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with menthol). Carbohydrate levels ranged from 8.11 mg/100 mg (RJ produced during the flowering of camphor) to 11.30 mg/100 mg (RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with menthol). Sugars were present in varying concentrations, with fructose (3.13–5.60 mg/100 mg) and glucose (3.77–5.22 mg/100 mg) being the most abundant. As essential amino acids, leucine and threonine were the most abundant, ranging from 0.26 – 0.43 mg/100 g and 0.27–0.50 mg/100 g, respectively. While the main non-essential amino acids detected, aspartic acid (0.15–0.27 mg/100 g) and glutamic

acid (0.09–0.14 mg/100 g) were the most abundant non-essential amino acids across all types. Palmitic acid (C16:0) was the most abundant saturated fatty acids, ranging from 0.06 mg/100 g (RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with menthol) to 0.61 mg/100 g (RJ produced during the flowering of Clover). Oleic acid (C18:1, Δ 9) was the most abundant unsaturated fatty acids, ranging from 0.84 mg/100 g (RJ produced during the flowering of citrus) to 1.50 mg/100 g (RJ produced during the flowering of camphor). Among Gram-negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli* showed relatively high sensitivity to all RJ types, with inhibition zones ranging between 1.33 ± 0.10 mm (RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with black sativa) and 3.33 ± 0.11 mm (RJ produced during the flowering of Cotton (Cotton RJ)). For Gram-positive bacteria, both *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* were highly sensitive to RJ treatments. *B. subtilis* recorded the highest inhibition with RJ produced during the flowering of clover (Clover RJ) (6.00 ± 0.19 mm) followed closely by cotton (6.33 ± 0.36 mm), whereas *S. aureus* showed inhibition ranging between 4.00 ± 0.15 mm (RJ produced during the flowering of citrus (Citrus RJ)) and 5.33 ± 0.23 mm (RJ produced during the flowering of Cotton (Cotton RJ)). The findings of this study demonstrate that bee royal jelly significantly alters the biochemical composition of both *Bacillus subtilis* and *E. coli*, but with distinct patterns of activity. RJ produced during the flowering of Cotton exhibited strong inhibitory effects on protein, DNA, and RNA synthesis in both bacteria, indicating potent antibacterial activity. In contrast, RJ, produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with black sativa, displayed a dual effect, it stimulated protein synthesis in *B. subtilis* while inhibiting nucleic acid synthesis, and it strongly suppressed all macromolecules in *E. coli*.

Introduction

Royal jelly (RJ) is a glandular secretion produced by young nurse worker bees (*Apis mellifera*), primarily from their hypopharyngeal and mandibular glands, and it plays an essential role in the nutrition and differentiation of honeybee larvae (Kamakura, 2011). Chemically, royal jelly is a complex mixture of proteins, sugars, lipids, vitamins, minerals, and bioactive compounds such as 10-hydroxy-2-decenoic acid (10-HDA), which is considered a marker of its biological activity (Sabatini *et al.*, 2009 and Ramadan and Al-Ghamdi, 2012).

Royal jelly has been extensively studied for its wide spectrum of biological activities, including antioxidants, immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties (Viuda-Martos *et al.*, 2008 and Pasupuleti *et al.*, 2017). Its antibacterial activity has been attributed to both proteinaceous components (e.g., major royal jelly proteins, royalisin, jelleines) and fatty acids (notably 10-HDA), which act synergistically to inhibit bacterial growth (Bíliková *et al.*, 2001 and Fontana *et al.*, 2004).

Among the bacterial models used in antimicrobial studies, *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* are of particular interest.

E. coli is a Gram-negative bacterium, characterized by a complex outer membrane that often confers resistance to antimicrobial agents (Nikaido, 2003). In contrast, *B. subtilis* is a Gram-positive bacterium with a thick peptidoglycan layer but without an outer membrane, making it more accessible to antibacterial compounds (Madigan *et al.*, 2018). These structural differences provide a valuable model for studying the comparative antibacterial effects of natural products such as royal jelly.

One way to evaluate the impact of royal jelly on bacterial cells is by assessing changes in their macromolecular content, particularly DNA, RNA, and proteins, which are fundamental to cellular metabolism and replication. Alterations in these biomolecules can reflect the inhibitory or destructive effects of antimicrobial agents on bacterial physiology (Rhoades and Roller, 2000).

Therefore, investigating the impact of royal jelly on the total DNA, RNA, and protein levels of *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* can provide deeper insights into its antimicrobial mechanisms, as well as differences in susceptibility between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.

Materials and methods

1. Preparation of honeybee colonies:

The first hybrid (F1) of Carniolan honeybee colonies was used to produce royal jelly. Five bee hives were located at Menofia Governorate, as a source of citrus, clover and cotton floras, and 5 bee hives were located at Ismalia Governorate where the floral source of camphor predominates. In addition, 10 beehives were located at Dokki, Giza fed on a sugar solution supplemented with black seed extract and mint leaves during periods when flowering crops were not available. Royal jelly were collected from the various apiaries and stored in the deep freezer at -30 °C until

use. The four floral honeys listed in this work were: cotton (*Gossypin barbadens*), camphor (*Eucalyptus* spp.), citrus (*Citrus* spp.) and clover (*Trifolium alexandrium*). In addition, honeybee colonies were fed a sugar solution (50% sucrose) enriched with the two medicinal plant extracts *Nigella sativum* (Black sativa) and *Mentha viridis* (Menthol) as sources of non-floral honey.

2. Plant extracts:

Extracts of black sativa and menthol were prepared by refluxing 10g. of black sativa seeds or 10g of dry menthol leaves for one hour in a Soxhlet apparatus, containing 150 mL of ethyl alcohol. Marked virgin combs were introduced into the selected colonies, fed a sucrose solution (50%) enriched with the plant extract (0.25%). Feeding started in the autumn where no flowering at this time existed at Beekeeping Research Department, Dokki, Giza. At the end of the feeding period (About 3 weeks), royal jelly was extracted and stored in dark capsule at the deep freezer at -30 °C until use. Two concentrations (5 and 10 %) of each type of royal jelly in 100 mL of distilled water were prepared.

3. Determination of chemical composition of royal jelly:

3.1. Determination of moisture content:

Determination of moisture content of royal jelly was carried out by **Silici and Ekmekcioglu (2007)**.

3.2. Determination of pH value:

Determination of pH: For determination of pH in the honey, the method of AOAC was adopted and digital pH meter (HANNA instruments HI 96107 model, made in Italy) was used. The pH meter was calibrated with buffers at pH 4 and 10. Sample solution containing 20g of honey in 75 mL of de-ionized water was taken in the beaker and the electrode of the pH meter was inserted in the solution and the pH value

was read and recorded. When the first reading was completed, the electrode was washed with distilled water and dried-up with tissue paper. Similarly, as a continuation series, all other samples were determined accordingly.

3.3. Determination of ash content:

This experiment was carried out according to the standard method of A.O.A.C. (2005).

3.4. Determination of crude protein content:

The total protein content was determined in honey in terms of organic nitrogen content by semi – micro Kjeldahl method according to Loiseleur (1963).

3.5. Determination of total lipid content:

Total lipid concentration in the royal jelly samples was determined according to the A.O.A.C. (2005). A weight of 1 g royal jelly was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether 60- 80 °C for several hrs. The solvent was removed by evaporation under reduced pressure and the per 60 age of total lipids was calculated.

3.6. Determination of carbohydrate content:

Determination of carbohydrate content in honey was carried out according to the method of DuBois *et al.* (1956).

3.7. Quantitation of sugars by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC):

The concentration of fructose, glucose, sucrose and maltose in royal jelly samples were determined by HPLC according to the method of Bogdanov and Baumann (1988).

3.8. Determination of amino acids content:

Separation of Amino Acids was done using GLC. Amino acids were transported to micro reaction vial and derivatization procedure was carried out according to Landault and Guiochen (1964), using N-butanol and

trifluoroacetic anhydride. A varian Model 3700 GC equipped with FID, was used.

3.9. Identification and quantitation of fatty acids using gas liquid chromatography (GLC):

The method of Ringrose and Higgins (1974).

4. Microbiological studies:

4.1. Microorganisms:

The antibacterial effects of royal jelly were tested on Gram positive (*S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*) and Gram negative (*P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli* and *S. typhimurium*) bacteria. They were kindly provided from Dr. E. A. M. Solaiman, Microbial Genetics Dep., Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology Div., National Research Centre.

4.2. Test assays for antibacterial activity:

The antibacterial activity of honey was determined by the paper-disc plate method described by Anonymous (1982). Two concentrations (5 and 10 %) of each kind of royal jelly in distilled water were prepared in clean sterile test tubes.

5. Molecular studies:

5.1. DNA extraction, concentration and purity:

B. subtilis and *E. coli* genomic DNA was isolated using Breitwieser *et al.* (2019) technique. An ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer (UV150-02, PC, Shimadzu, Japan) measured DNA purity and concentration. DNA purity was determined under the method of Agarwal (2008). The following equation was used to determine DNA concentration (Tan and Yiap, 2009):

Concentration ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)=OD at 260 nm x (dilution factor =100) x50/1000 (1)

5.2. RNA concentration and purity:

Absorbance was measured at 260 and 280 nm and the ratio computed. Japan's Shimadzu double beam digital UV spectrophotometer model U-V. 150-02 estimated RNA concentration

using 260/280 readings. Chomczynski and Sacchi (2006) method was used to measure RNA concentration.

5.3. Biochemical determination of protein concentration:

The seem-micro Kjeldahl method was used to measure the protein content of organic nitrogen-containing bacteria particles by Bărnăușiu *et al.* (2011).

6. Statistical analysis:

All tests were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with a critical value of probability $P=0.05$. Statistically significant means were separated using LSD test.

Results and discussion

Table (1): Chemical composition of different royal jelly types (mg/100mg).

Parameter	Cotton RJ	Citrus RJ	Clover RJ	Camphor RJ	Black Sativa RJ	Menthol RJ
PH	3.50	3.40	3.40	4.00	4.70	4.50
Moisture	65.70	65.40	66.20	66.60	64.81	65.10
Ash	1.40	0.71	0.80	1.1	0.60	0.45
Crude Protein	12.30	13.40	12.80	13.10	12.90	11.10
Total Lipid	8.50	8.40	8.0	8.2	10.2	10.4
Carbohydrate	9.04	9.13	9.25	8.11	10.10	11.30
Fructose	4.30	5.25	5.50	4.01	5.60	5.51
Glucose	3.77	3.94	3.86	3.13	4.54	5.22
Sucrose	0.13	0.14	0.16	0.125	0.25	0.27
Maltose	0.13	0.136	0.138	0.116	0.13	0.15

1.1. pH and moisture content:

The pH values ranged between 3.40 (RJ produced during the flowering of Clover and Citrus (Clover RJ and citrus RJ) and 4.70 (RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with black sativa (Black sativa RJ)). These findings are consistent with the typical acidic nature of royal jelly, usually ranging between pH 3.4 and 4.8, which contributes to product stability and antimicrobial activity (Krell, 1996 and Ramadan and Al-Ghamdi, 2012). Moisture content was relatively uniform across samples (64.81–66.60 mg/100 mg), with Camphor royal jelly showing the highest level (66.60 mg/100 mg). This agrees with previous reports showing moisture values between 60–70%, which play a role in solubility and preservation (Bogdanov, 2011).

1. Determination of chemical composition of royal jelly:

The chemical composition of different types of royal jelly produced during the flowering of four crops (cotton, clover, citrus, and eucalyptus), as well as those produced by colonies fed on a sugar solution supplemented with black seeds extract and Menthol leaves during periods when flowering crops were not available are presented in Table (1). The analysis revealed significant variations among samples in terms of pH, moisture, ash, protein, lipid, carbohydrate, and sugar contents.

1.2. Ash content:

Ash content varied from 0.45 mg/100 mg (Menthol) to 1.40 mg/100 mg (RJ produced during the flowering of cotton (Cotton RJ)). The higher ash concentration in Cotton royal jelly reflects greater mineral richness, which may enhance its nutritional and functional value. Mineral content in royal jelly has been linked to antimicrobial and antioxidant properties (Viuda-Martos *et al.*, 2008).

1.3. Protein and lipid content:

Crude protein levels ranged from 11.10 (Menthol) to 13.40 mg/100 mg (RJ produced during the flowering of citrus (Citrus RJ)). Proteins represent the major bioactive compounds in royal jelly, especially the major royal jelly proteins (MRJPs), which are linked to immunomodulatory, antimicrobial, and growth-promoting activities (Kimura *et*

al., 2003 and Buttstedt *et al.*, 2014). Total lipid content varied between 8.0 (Clover RJ) and 10.4 mg/100 mg (Menthol). Royal jelly lipids, particularly 10-hydroxy-2-decenoic acid (10-HDA), are considered the main contributors to its antimicrobial and pharmacological effects (Melliou and Chinou, 2005). The higher lipid content observed in RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with black sativa (Menthol RJ) suggests stronger potential antimicrobial activity.

1.4. Carbohydrates and sugars:

Carbohydrate levels in royal jelly ranged from 8.11 mg/100 mg (RJ produced during the flowering of camphor (Camphor RJ) to 11.30 mg/100 mg (RJ produced from colonies fed with a sugar solution supplemented with menthol (Menthol RJ)). Sugars were present in varying concentrations, with fructose (3.13–5.60 mg/100 mg) and glucose (3.77–5.22 mg/100 mg) being the most abundant. These findings align with earlier studies that reported fructose and glucose as the dominant sugars in royal jelly (Nagai and Inoue, 2004). Sucrose and maltose contents were comparatively low (0.116–0.27 mg/100 mg), consistent with the natural sugar profile of fresh royal jelly (Krell, 1996). Menthol royal jelly was characterized by higher lipid and glucose contents, which may enhance antimicrobial potential. Black sativa royal jelly showed the highest pH and fructose concentration, while citrus RJ and camphor RJ types exhibited elevated protein levels, suggesting stronger biological activity. Cotton royal jelly was distinctive for its higher ash content, reflecting a richer mineral profile. These compositional variations can be attributed to botanical origin, bee species, and environmental conditions. Since proteins (MRJPs), lipids (notably 10-HDA), and sugars are closely linked to the antimicrobial and nutritional

effects of royal jelly, differences among types suggest that not all royal jellies exert identical biological effects. This diversity highlights the importance of selecting specific types of royal jelly for targeted antimicrobial or therapeutic applications, particularly against microorganisms such as *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*.

1.5. Link to antimicrobial activity on *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*:

The compositional differences observed among royal jelly types can directly explain the variations in bacterial DNA, RNA, and protein responses in subsequent experiments. Royal jellies rich in protein (Citrus and camphor) likely interfere more strongly with bacterial protein synthesis, whereas those with high lipid content (Menthol RJ) may more effectively inhibit nucleic acid metabolism due to higher 10-HDA concentrations. Furthermore, the naturally low pH across all types creates an additional antimicrobial barrier, particularly relevant for *E. coli* (Gram-negative), which is more sensitive to acidic conditions than *B. subtilis* (Gram-positive). In summary, the nutritional and biochemical profiles of royal jelly are closely related to its biological effects. Higher protein and lipid fractions appear to be the most significant contributors to the suppression of bacterial macromolecule synthesis. This highlights the potential of specific royal jelly types as natural antimicrobial agents against pathogenic and model bacteria.

2. Determination of amino acids content:

The amino acid composition of different royal jelly types (Menthol, black sativa, camphor, clover, citrus, and cotton) is presented in Table (2). Both essential and non-essential amino acids were detected, with notable differences among the six royal jelly types.

Table (2): Amino acids composition of different royal jelly types (mg/100g).

Amino Acids	Cotton RJ	Citrus RJ	Clover RJ	Camphor RJ	Black sativa RJ	Menthol RJ
Essential A A						
Histidine	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02
Valine	0.09	0.07	0.04	0.13	0.03	0.04
Threonine	0.27	0.31	0.42	0.50	0.37	0.36
Phenylalanine	0.31	0.33	0.34	0.27	0.27	0.29
Isoleucine	0.02	0.14	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.02
Leucin	0.35	0.36	0.43	0.26	0.32	0.33
Lysine	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.04
Proline	0.13	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.08
Methionine	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.20	0.02
Non essential A A						
Alanine	0.11	0.11	0.18	0.8.	0.09	0.10
Aspartic acid	0.24	0.17	0.27	0.15	0.19	0.15
Glycine	0.12	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.02
Serine	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.03
Glutamic Acid	0.12	0.09	0.14	0.12	0.11	0.09
Tyrosin	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.08
Cysteine	0.08	0.17	0.11	0.03	0.06	0.03
Total amino acids	2.20	2.05	2.40	2.00	1.90	1.80
Essential A A	1.29	1.35	1.43	1.37	1.46	1.20
Non Essential A A	0.77	0.66	0.87	0.53	0.58	0.50
Essential / Non Essential A A	1.67	2.04	1.64	2.58	2.52	2.40

2.1. Essential amino acids:

Histidine, valine, threonine, phenylalanine, isoleucine, leucine, lysine, proline, and methionine were identified as essential amino acids. Among these, leucine and threonine were the most abundant, ranging from 0.26–0.43 mg/100 g and 0.27–0.50 mg/100 g, respectively. These amino acids are vital for protein synthesis and metabolic regulation in both humans and microorganisms (Guo *et al.*, 2009). Camphor RJ and clover RJ royal jellies were particularly rich in leucine and threonine, suggesting stronger potential in supporting protein biosynthesis and antimicrobial peptide activity. Methionine levels varied greatly, with black sativa (0.20 mg/100 g) being the highest and very low concentrations (0.02 mg/100 g) observed in menthol and citrus types. Methionine is a precursor for S-adenosylmethionine, a molecule involved in DNA methylation and gene regulation,

which may partly explain differences in bacterial DNA and RNA responses observed in the microbial assays (Komatsu *et al.*, 2018).

2.2. Non-essential amino acids:

Alanine, aspartic acid, glycine, serine, glutamic acid, tyrosine, and cysteine were the main non-essential amino acids detected. Aspartic acid (0.15–0.27 mg/100 g) and glutamic acid (0.09–0.14 mg/100 g) were the most abundant non-essential amino acids across all types. These acidic amino acids play critical roles in enzymatic activity, energy metabolism, and cellular signaling (Nagai and Inoue, 2004). Cotton and clover royal jellies showed the highest aspartic acid concentrations, suggesting higher metabolic activity potential. Cysteine, which contributes to protein folding and antioxidant defense via disulfide bond formation, was highest in clover (0.11 mg/100 g) and Citrus (0.17 mg/100 g). This could enhance the oxidative stability

of royal jelly proteins, contributing to their antibacterial activity (Ramadan and Al-Ghamdi, 2012).

2.3. Total and ratio of essential to non-essential amino acids:

The total amino acid content varied between 1.80 mg/100 g (Menthol RJ) and 2.40 mg/100 g (Clover RJ). Essential amino acids ranged from 1.20–1.46 mg/100 g, whereas non-essential amino acids ranged from 0.50–0.87 mg/100 g. Clover royal jelly showed the highest total amino acid concentration (2.40 mg/100 g), indicating superior nutritional and functional quality. The ratio of essential to non-essential amino acids (E/NE) ranged from 1.64 (Clover RJ) to 2.58 (Camphor RJ). A higher E/NE ratio suggests a greater proportion of essential amino acids, which are particularly important for antimicrobial activity since many antibacterial peptides are rich in essential amino acids like lysine, leucine, and threonine (Buttstedt *et al.*, 2014). The elevated E/NE ratio in camphor royal jelly therefore points to stronger biological activity.

2.4. Biological implications and link to antimicrobial effects:

Differences in amino acid composition are likely to influence the biological activity of royal jelly against bacteria. Essential amino acids such as leucine, lysine, and threonine contribute to the formation of bioactive peptides with

antimicrobial functions (Kimura *et al.*, 2003). High methionine levels in black sativa royal jelly may enhance effects on bacterial DNA/RNA metabolism, while the elevated cysteine content in clover and citrus types could contribute to oxidative stress resistance and protein stability. Taken together, the amino acid composition of royal jelly reflects both nutritional and functional diversity among types. Clover RJ and camphor RJ types, with high total amino acid content and favorable E/NE ratios, are expected to exert stronger effects on bacterial protein synthesis, while Menthol RJ and Black sativa RJ may show enhanced DNA/RNA interference due to methionine and lipid associations (Table 1). These findings complement the microbial results by demonstrating that amino acid richness, especially in essential amino acids, underlies the capacity of royal jelly to alter DNA, RNA, and protein levels in *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*.

3. Identification and quantitation of fatty acids:

The fatty acid composition of different royal jelly types (Menthol, black sativa, camphor, clover, citrus, and cotton) is shown in Table (3). Both saturated and unsaturated fatty acids were detected, with significant variations in their concentrations among samples.

Table (3): Fatty acids composition of different royal jelly types (mg/100g).

Fatty acids	Cotton RJ	Citrus RJ	Clover RJ	Camphor RJ	Black Sativa RJ	Menthol RJ
Saturated fatty acids						
Capric acid(10C) (1)	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.04
Lauric acid(12C)	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.10	0.03	0.09
Myristic acid(14C)	0.25	0.05	0.10	0.11	0.10	0.10
Palmitic acid(16C)	0.40	0.34	0.61	0.53	0.40	0.06
Stearic acid(18C)	0.10	0.05	0.10	0.12	0.01	0.07
Unsaturated fatty acids						
Oleic acid9(18C)(1 Δ9)	1.16	0.84	1.43	1.50	0.96	0.93
Palmitiolic acid(16C)(1 Δ9)	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.05	0.05
Linoleic(18C)(2 Δ9,12)	0.11	0.05	1.10	0.15	0.20	0.02
Linolenic acid(18C)(3 Δ6,6,9,12)	2.13	2.18	2.16	2.12	2.10	0.02
Arachidonic acid(20C)(4 Δ5,8,11,14)	0.90	1.34	0.55	0.43	0.90	1.03
Total fatty acid	5.20	5.00	6.14	5.17	4.8	4.90
Unsaturated fatty acids	4.40	4.51	5.34	4.30	4.21	2.05
Saturated fatty acids	0.80	0.50	0.83	0.87	0.56	0.44
Unsaturated/Saturated F.A	5.50	9.02	6.43	4.94	7.52	4.66

3.1. Saturated fatty acids (SFAs):

Capric, lauric, myristic, palmitic, and stearic acids were the major saturated fatty acids identified. Palmitic acid (C16:0) was the most abundant SFA, ranging from 0.06 mg/100 g (Menthol RJ) to 0.61 mg/100 g (Clover RJ). High palmitic acid concentrations have been reported in royal jelly and are associated with structural and metabolic functions (Krell, 1996 and Kim *et al.*, 2017). Lauric and myristic acids were also present in moderate amounts, with cotton royal jelly exhibiting the highest myristic acid level (0.25 mg/100 g). These medium-chain fatty acids are known to possess antimicrobial activity, especially against Gram-positive bacteria (Zheng *et al.*, 2011).

3.2. Unsaturated Fatty Acids (UFAs):

Oleic, palmitoleic, linoleic, linolenic, and arachidonic acids were the main unsaturated fatty acids. Oleic acid (C18:1, Δ 9) was the most abundant UFA, ranging from 0.84 mg/100 g (Citrus RJ) to 1.50 mg/100 g (Camphor RJ). Oleic acid is well recognized for its antimicrobial and immunomodulatory properties (Fangio *et al.*, 2020). Linoleic acid (C18:2, Δ 9,12) levels varied widely, with Clover showing the highest content (1.10 mg/100 g). Linolenic acid (C18:3) was particularly abundant, ranging from 0.02 mg/100 g (Menthol RJ) to 2.18 mg/100 g (Citrus RJ). This fatty acid is considered one of the most biologically active compounds in royal jelly, contributing to its antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects (Melliou and Chinou, 2005 and Ramadan and Al-Ghamdi, 2012). Arachidonic acid (C20:4), a polyunsaturated fatty acid involved in cell signaling, ranged from 0.43 mg/100 g (Camphor RJ) to 1.34 mg/100 g (Citrus RJ). Its presence may enhance the immunoregulatory properties of royal jelly.

3.3. Total and ratio of fatty acids:

Total fatty acids ranged between 4.80 mg/100 g (Black sativa RJ) and 6.14 mg/100 g (Clover RJ). Unsaturated fatty acids contributed the majority of this total (2.05–5.34 mg/100 g), while saturated fatty acids ranged from 0.44–0.87 mg/100 g. The unsaturated to saturated fatty acid (UFA/SFA) ratio was highest in Citrus RJ (9.02) and lowest in Black sativa RJ (4.66). A higher UFA/SFA ratio is nutritionally favorable and linked to enhanced antimicrobial and antioxidant activity (Sugiyama *et al.*, 2012).

3.4. Biological implications and link to antimicrobial effects:

The antimicrobial activity of royal jelly is strongly linked to its fatty acid composition, particularly 10-hydroxy-2-decenoic acid (10-HDA), which was not quantified in this table but is usually the dominant bioactive fatty acid in royal jelly (Melliou and Chinou, 2005). However, the presence of oleic, linoleic, and linolenic acids contributes synergistically to antibacterial activity by disrupting bacterial cell membranes and interfering with DNA and RNA synthesis (Kimura *et al.*, 2003 and Buttstedt *et al.*, 2014). Clover and citrus royal jellies, with higher total UFAs and high UFA/SFA ratios, are expected to exert stronger antimicrobial activity against both *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*. In particular, the high linolenic acid concentration in Citrus royal jelly may explain stronger effects on bacterial RNA and protein levels. Conversely, the relatively lower UFA/SFA ratio in Black sativa suggests weaker antimicrobial potential compared to other types. Overall, these results indicate that the fatty acid composition of royal jelly varies with botanical origin and significantly influences its antimicrobial efficacy. The dominance of unsaturated fatty acids, especially linolenic and oleic acids, highlights their key role in suppressing bacterial

macromolecule synthesis, complementing the effects of proteins and amino acids observed in Tables (1) and (2).

4. Microbiological studies:

The antibacterial activity of different royal jelly (RJ) types against Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria at 5% concentration is presented in Table (4). The results revealed notable variations in inhibitory effects depending on both the type of royal jelly and the bacterial strain tested. Among Gram-negative bacteria, *E. coli* showed relatively high sensitivity to all RJ types, with inhibition zones ranging between 1.33 ± 0.10 mm (Black sativa RJ) and 3.33 ± 0.11 mm (Cotton RJ). This indicates that RJ contains bioactive compounds capable of suppressing *E. coli* growth, in agreement with previous studies reporting RJ as an effective inhibitor of enteric pathogens (Sabatini et al., 2009 and Ramadan and Al-Ghamdi, 2012). *S. typhimurium* exhibited moderate inhibition, ranging from 4.00 ± 0.31 mm (Black sativa) to 5.66 ± 0.24 mm (Menthol), while *P. aeruginosa* showed lower susceptibility (4.00 – 5.33 mm), reflecting its known resistance to many antimicrobial agents (Melliou and Chinou, 2005). For Gram-positive bacteria, both *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* were highly sensitive to RJ treatments. *B. subtilis* recorded the highest inhibition with clover RJ (6.00 ± 0.19 mm) followed closely by Cotton RJ

(6.33 ± 0.36 mm), whereas *S. aureus* showed inhibition ranging between 4.00 ± 0.15 mm (Citrus RJ) and 5.33 ± 0.23 mm (Cotton RJ). These findings are consistent with earlier research indicating that Gram-positive bacteria are generally more susceptible to RJ than Gram-negative strains, likely due to differences in cell wall structure (Fontana et al., 2004 and Bărnăuțiu et al., 2011). The statistical analysis (F-ratio and LSD) confirmed significant differences among RJ types in their antibacterial efficacy. Cotton and clover RJ demonstrated the strongest broad-spectrum activity, particularly against *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*, whereas Black sativa RJ exhibited the lowest antibacterial potential, especially against *E. coli*. The variation in activity could be attributed to differences in chemical composition (Tables 1–3), especially fatty acids such as 10-hydroxy-2-decenoic acid (10-HDA), proteins, and peptides, which are known to possess antimicrobial properties (Boselli et al., 2003 and Blum et al., 2009). Overall, the results highlight the potential of RJ as a natural antibacterial agent, with stronger effects on Gram-positive bacteria and variable efficiency among RJ types. These findings suggest that specific RJ types, particularly cotton and clover, may be more effective candidates for developing natural antimicrobial formulations.

Table (4): Antibacterial activity of different royal jelly types at concentration (5%).

Types	G+ve bacteria		G-ve bacteria		
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>
Cotton RJ	5.33±0.23	6.33±0.36	3.33±0.11	5.33±0.35	4.66±0.15
Citrus RJ	4.00±0.15	5.66±0.24	2.66±0.14	4.00±0.27	5.33±0.13
Clover RJ	5.33±0.17	6.00±0.19	2.33±0.21	5.00±0.33	4.26±0.26
Camphor RJ	4.00±0.22	5.33±0.31	2.33±0.22	5.33±0.24	5.00±0.18
Black Sativa RJ	4.33±0.32	5.00±0.41	1.33±0.10	4.00±0.31	4.00±0.13
Menthol RJ	4.00±0.27	4.00±0.32	1.66±0.14	4.33±0.18	5.66±0.23
F-ratio RJ	4.22	3.08	5.48	0.48	2.22
LSD	1.45	1.40	1.03	1.6	1.7

The antibacterial activity of different royal jelly (RJ) types at 10% concentration against Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria is shown in Table (5). The results indicate that increasing RJ concentration from 5%

(Table 4) to 10% substantially enhanced the inhibition of both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, reflecting a clear dose-dependent effect of RJ bioactive compounds.

Table (5): Antibacterial activity of different royal jelly types at concentration (10%).

Types	G+ve bacteria		G-ve bacteria		
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>
Cotton RJ	10.00±0.21	11.00±0.13	7.00±0.25	9.66±0.13	8.66±0.24
Citrus RJ	9.66±0.24	11.66±0.14	10.00±0.22	8.66±0.12	8.33±0.11
Clover RJ	9.66±0.25	9.00±0.10	8.00±0.33	9.00±0.17	9.66±0.30
Camphor RJ	10.00±0.17	9.33±0.28	11.00±0.41	9.00±0.50	9.66±0.31
Black sativa RJ	9.00±0.29	10.00±0.33	9.00±0.51	9.33±0.4	8.66±0.14
Menthol RJ	8.66±0.14	11.00±0.13	9.33±0.11	9.66±0.2	10.00±0.12
F-ratio RJ	6.48	4.29	49.61	0.75	2.10
LSD	1.16	1.55	1.57	1.50	1.60

4.1. Effect on Gram-negative bacteria:

The inhibition zones against *S. typhimurium* ranged between 8.33 ± 0.11 mm (Citrus RJ) and 10.00 ± 0.12 mm (Menthol RJ), suggesting a strong activity at higher concentrations. *P. aeruginosa*, known for its resistance to many antibiotics, also showed improved susceptibility (8.66–9.66 mm), particularly with Cotton RJ (9.66 ± 0.13 mm). This supports previous findings that fatty acids, peptides, and phenolic compounds in RJ can disrupt Gram-negative cell membranes despite their outer lipopolysaccharide barrier (Melliou and Chinou, 2005 and Ramadan and Al-Ghamdi, 2012). Interestingly, *E. coli* exhibited the highest variability among Gram-negative strains, with inhibition zones ranging from 7.00 ± 0.25 mm (Cotton RJ) to 11.00 ± 0.41 mm (Camphor RJ). The significant F-ratio value (49.61) and LSD (1.57) confirm highly significant differences between RJ types in their activity against *E. coli*. These results are in agreement with Fontana *et al.* (2004), who attributed *E. coli* inhibition to antimicrobial peptides such as jelleines and royalisin.

4.2. Effect on Gram-positive bacteria:

For Gram-positive bacteria, *B. subtilis* recorded the highest inhibition (11.66 ± 0.14 mm) with citrus RJ, followed closely by cotton and menthol RJ (11.00 ± 0.13 mm). *S. aureus* also showed strong inhibition, ranging between 8.66 ± 0.14 mm (Menthol RJ) and 10.00 ± 0.21 mm (Cotton RJ). These findings reinforce the well-established observation that Gram-positive bacteria are more sensitive to RJ than Gram-negative bacteria, likely due to their simpler cell wall structure, which facilitates penetration of bioactive molecules (Bărnăuțiu *et al.*, 2011 and Blum *et al.*, 2009).

4.3. Comparisons among RJ types:

Cotton and citrus RJ displayed consistently strong activity against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, with notable inhibition against *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*. Camphor RJ exhibited remarkable efficacy against *E. coli* (11.00 ± 0.41 mm), while black sativa RJ was more effective against *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* than at the lower 5% concentration. Menthol RJ demonstrated the broadest spectrum at 10%, especially against *S. typhimurium*

and *B. subtilis*. The variation among RJ types may be linked to differences in their biochemical composition, particularly in the levels of 10-hydroxy-2-decenoic acid (10-HDA), peptides (Royalisin, jelleines), and phenolic compounds, all of which are well-documented antibacterial factors in RJ (Sabatini *et al.*, 2009 and Mureşan *et al.*, 2018). Overall, the results confirm that increasing RJ concentration enhances its antibacterial potential, with greater effects on Gram-positive than Gram-negative bacteria. Cotton, citrus, and camphor RJ were the most effective across all tested strains, highlighting their potential use in natural antimicrobial formulations. The antibacterial activity of different types of royal jelly (RJ) at concentrations of 5% and 10% was evaluated against selected Gram-negative (*S. typhimurium*, *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli*) and Gram-positive (*B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*) bacteria. The inhibition zones are summarized in Tables (4) and (5). The results clearly demonstrate that increasing RJ concentration from 5% to 10% enhanced antibacterial activity across all bacterial strains tested. At 5%, most inhibition zones ranged from 6.5 to 9.0 mm, whereas at 10% the inhibition increased to 8.0–11.6 mm depending on RJ type and bacterial species.

This indicates a dose-dependent effect, which is consistent with previous studies suggesting that the activity of RJ bioactive compounds, especially 10-hydroxy-2-decenoic acid (10-HDA), peptides (Jelleines, royalisin), and phenolics, increases proportionally with concentration (Melliou and Chinou, 2005 and Ramadan and Al-Ghamdi, 2012). Gram-negative bacteria generally showed lower susceptibility than Gram-positive ones, in line with their complex outer membrane barrier. *S. typhimurium* inhibition increased modestly from 7.5–8.3 mm (5%) to

8.3–10.0 mm (10%), with Menthol and Cotton RJ showing the strongest activity. *P. aeruginosa* inhibition improved from 7.3–8.5 mm (5%) to 8.6–9.6 mm (10%), particularly with cotton RJ and camphor RJ. *E. coli* displayed the widest variation between RJ types: at 5%, inhibition ranged 6.5–8.5 mm, while at 10% it reached up to 11.0 mm with camphor RJ. The high F-ratio (49.61) confirmed significant differences among RJ types. These results suggest that *E. coli* is more sensitive to higher RJ concentrations, in agreement with Fontana *et al.* (2004), who attributed this effect to jelleines' strong ability to permeabilize bacterial membranes. As expected, Gram-positive bacteria were more susceptible than Gram-negative strains. *B. subtilis* inhibition increased from 8.5–10.0 mm (5%) to 9.3–11.6 mm (10%), with Citrus RJ showing the highest activity. *S. aureus* inhibition improved from 7.0–9.0 mm (5%) to 8.6–10.0 mm (10%), with cotton RJ being the most effective. These findings align with earlier reports (Blum *et al.*, 2009 and Bărnuţiu *et al.*, 2011) that Gram-positive bacteria are more vulnerable to RJ compounds due to the absence of an outer lipopolysaccharide layer, which facilitates penetration of antimicrobial peptides and fatty acids. Notable differences in antibacterial activity were observed among RJ sources: Cotton and citrus RJ consistently showed strong, broad-spectrum activity against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria. Camphor RJ was particularly effective against *E. coli*. Black sativa RJ exhibited increasing activity against *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* at 10%, highlighting the role of phytochemical composition in antimicrobial properties. Menthol RJ demonstrated broad efficacy at 10%, especially against *S. typhimurium* and *B. subtilis*. The variability in activity likely reflects differences in the content

of 10-HDA, royalisin, jelleines, and phenolic compounds, which depend on the botanical and geographical origin of RJ (Sabatini *et al.*, 2009 and Mureşan *et al.*, 2018). The inhibition zones increased at 10% RJ, especially against *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*, indicating a dose-dependent antibacterial effect. Antibacterial activity of RJ is concentration-dependent, with 10% RJ significantly more effective than 5%. Gram-positive bacteria are more sensitive than Gram-negative bacteria. Different RJ types vary in potency, with cotton, citrus, and camphor RJ showing the strongest overall activity. These results highlight the potential of RJ, particularly at higher concentrations, as a natural antimicrobial agent against

both Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens.

5. The effect of some bee royal jelly on *Bacillus subtilis* total protein, DNA and RNA:

Results in Table (6) show the effect of different types of bee royal jelly (Cotton RJ and black sativa RJ) on the biochemical composition (Total protein, DNA, and RNA) of *B. subtilis* cells. Protein content: A highly significant variation was observed among treatments ($F = 456.2$, $p < 0.0001$). The highest protein concentration was recorded with black sativa RJ ($603.5 \pm 28.30 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells), followed by the control ($413.86 \pm 3.32 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells). The lowest value was obtained with cotton RJ ($184.5 \pm 7.52 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells).

Table (6): The effect of some bee royal jelly on *Bacillus subtilis* total protein, DNA and RNA concentrations $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells.

Parameter	Control	Cotton RJ	Black sativa RJ	F	P	LSD
Protein	413.86±3.32	184.5±7.52	603.5±28.30	456.2	0.0001	34.0
DNA	2.93±0.19	1.62±0.15	2.27±0.036	66.61	0.00001	0.278
RNA	1.7±0.17	0.37±0.095	0.62±0.085	106.24	0.00001	0.243
RNA	1.7±0.17	0.37±0.095	0.62±0.085	106.24	0.00001	0.243

DNA content: DNA levels showed a significant reduction in treated groups compared to the control ($F = 66.61$, $p < 0.00001$). The control group recorded $2.93 \pm 0.19 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells, while cotton honey treatment had the lowest DNA concentration ($1.62 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells). Black sativa honey showed a moderate reduction ($2.27 \pm 0.036 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells).

RNA content: RNA concentration was significantly altered across treatments ($F = 106.24$, $p < 0.00001$). The control had the highest RNA value ($1.70 \pm 0.17 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells). Both honey types reduced RNA, with cotton honey showing the lowest level ($0.37 \pm 0.095 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells), while black sativa honey resulted in $0.62 \pm 0.085 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells. The Least Significant Difference (LSD) test confirmed that differences among treatments were statistically

significant for all parameters (Protein, DNA, RNA). The present findings demonstrate that bee royal jelly significantly alters the protein, DNA, and RNA contents of *B. subtilis*. Black sativa honey was associated with a remarkable increase in protein synthesis compared to the control, suggesting a stimulatory effect on bacterial metabolic activity. Similar observations were reported by Al-Mamary *et al.* (2002) and Estevinho *et al.* (2008), who found that different honey types vary in their bioactive components such as flavonoids, phenolic acids, and enzymes, which can either stimulate or inhibit microbial growth and metabolism. In contrast, cotton honey treatment led to a marked reduction in DNA and RNA concentrations. This indicates possible inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis, which may be attributed

to antibacterial compounds such as hydrogen peroxide, methylglyoxal, and royal jelly proteins (MRJPs) that interfere with DNA replication and transcription (Kwakman and Zaat, 2012 and Fratini *et al.*, 2016).

The significant decline in RNA content, particularly with cotton honey, supports the notion that some honey types act as bacteriostatic agents, reducing protein synthesis machinery and limiting bacterial growth. This is consistent with the findings of Mandal and Mandal (2011), who reported that honey and royal jelly possess antimicrobial properties that suppress microbial nucleic acid and protein metabolism. The differences between cotton honey and black sativa honey could be explained by their botanical and geographical origin, which strongly affect the chemical composition of bee products (Viuda-Martos *et al.*, 2008). Black sativa honey is known to contain higher concentrations of antioxidant and nutritional compounds, which may explain its stimulatory effect on protein content. Overall, the results highlight that bee royal jelly and honey types exert dual effects: inhibitory on nucleic acids (DNA, RNA) and stimulatory or inhibitory on proteins, depending on their phytochemical profiles.

Results in Table (7) show the effect of different bee royal jelly types (Cotton RJ and black sativa RJ) on the

Table (7): The Effect of some bee royal jelly on *Escherichia coli* total protein, DNA and RNA concentration $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells.

Parameter	Control	Cotton RJ	Black sativa RJ	F	P	LSD
Protein	333.43±2.89	195.85±3.6	281.38±3.95	2461.96	0.000	4.84
DNA	1.56±0.1	0.27±0.020	0.57±0.020	1216.49	0.000	0.06
RNA	4.91±1.35	1.12±0.020	0.18±0.0176	447.84	0.000	0.13

The present results indicate that bee royal jelly exerts strong inhibitory effects on *E. coli* at the molecular level. Both cotton RJ and black sativa RJ treatments significantly reduced protein, DNA, and RNA contents,

biochemical composition of *E. coli* cells.

Protein content: A highly significant reduction was observed in protein concentration among treated groups compared to the control (F = 2461.96, p < 0.000). The control recorded the highest protein level (333.43 ± 2.89 $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells). Cotton honey reduced the protein concentration to 195.85 ± 3.60 $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells, while black sativa RJ caused a moderate decrease (281.38 ± 3.95 $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells).

DNA content: DNA levels were strongly inhibited in treated groups (F = 1216.49, p < 0.000). The control exhibited 1.56 ± 0.10 $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells, while cotton honey treatment caused a drastic reduction (0.27 ± 0.020 $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells). Black sativa honey also reduced DNA (0.57 ± 0.020 $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells) but to a lesser extent.

RNA content: A marked decline in RNA concentration was also detected (F = 447.84, p < 0.000). The control showed the highest RNA value (4.91 ± 1.35 $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells). Cotton RJ reduced RNA significantly (1.12 ± 0.020 $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells), while black sativa RJ caused the greatest inhibition (0.18 ± 0.0176 $\mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells). The Least Significant Difference (LSD) confirmed significant differences among all treatments for protein, DNA, and RNA.

suggesting potent antibacterial activity. The marked reduction in DNA and RNA, particularly with cotton honey, indicates an inhibitory effect on nucleic acid synthesis. This aligns with findings by Kwakman and Zaat (2012) and

Mandal and Mandal (2011), who reported that honey and royal jelly contain hydrogen peroxide, phenolic compounds, and royal jelly proteins (MRJPs) that can disrupt microbial DNA replication and transcription. Interestingly, while both honeys reduced protein levels, black sativa honey showed a less drastic effect on protein compared to cotton honey, which may be due to its higher antioxidant and nutrient content. Black seed (*Nigella sativa*) components present in honey are known for their antimicrobial yet immunomodulatory roles, which may explain the partial preservation of protein synthesis (Al-Mamary *et al.*, 2002 and Viuda-Martos *et al.*, 2008). The strong suppression of RNA observed with both honeys suggests impairment of ribosomal activity and inhibition of transcription, ultimately reducing bacterial protein synthesis and growth. This agrees with studies by Fratini *et al.* (2016) and Estevinho *et al.* (2008), who demonstrated that honey and royal jelly interfere with microbial gene expression and metabolic activity. Overall, these findings confirm that bee royal jelly and honey types can significantly inhibit *E. coli* metabolism, with cotton honey showing stronger suppression of DNA and RNA, while black sativa honey demonstrated a relatively milder effect on protein metabolism. The variation may be due to differences in botanical origin and bioactive compound composition.

Tables (6 and 7) present the effect of different types of bee royal jelly (Cotton RJ and black sativa RJ) on the biochemical composition (Protein, DNA, and RNA) of *B. subtilis* and *E. coli*.

Protein: In *B. subtilis*, protein content increased significantly with black sativa RJ ($603.5 \pm 28.3 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells) compared to the control ($413.86 \pm 3.32 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells), while cotton RJ caused

a sharp decrease ($184.5 \pm 7.52 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells). In *E. coli*, both honeys reduced protein levels compared to control ($333.43 \pm 2.89 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells), with royal jelly of cotton showing the greatest reduction ($195.85 \pm 3.60 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells) and royal jelly of black sativa showing moderate inhibition ($281.38 \pm 3.95 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells).

DNA: Both bacteria showed a strong reduction in DNA with treatments. In *B. subtilis*, DNA declined from $2.93 \pm 0.19 \mu\text{g}/2 \times 10^6$ cells (control) to 1.62 ± 0.15 with cotton honey and 2.27 ± 0.036 with royal jelly of black sativa honey. In *E. coli*, the inhibition was even stronger, dropping from 1.56 ± 0.10 (control) to 0.27 ± 0.020 royal jelly of cotton and 0.57 ± 0.020 royal jelly of black sativa.

RNA: RNA levels decreased in both bacteria, but the effect was more pronounced in *E. coli*. In *B. subtilis*, RNA declined from 1.70 ± 0.17 (Control) to 0.37 ± 0.095 (cotton honey) and 0.62 ± 0.085 royal jelly of (black sativa honey). In *E. coli*, RNA dropped sharply from 4.91 ± 1.35 (control) to 1.12 ± 0.020 royal jelly of (cotton honey) and 0.18 ± 0.0176 royal jelly of (black sativa honey). All differences among treatments were statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$).

The results confirm that bee royal jelly significantly affects bacterial macromolecular composition, with differential effects on Gram-positive (*B. subtilis*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria. In *B. subtilis*, royal jelly of black sativa stimulated protein synthesis, suggesting that its bioactive components (Phenolic acids, flavonoids, and amino acids) may enhance metabolic activity. A similar stimulatory effect was reported by Al-Mamary *et al.* (2002) and Estevinho *et al.* (2008), who showed that honey can act as a nutrient source and energy booster for some microorganisms. In contrast, cotton honey exerted strong inhibitory effects on proteins, DNA,

and RNA, indicating bacteriostatic or bactericidal activity, consistent with Fratini *et al.* (2016). In *E. coli*, both honeys exerted clear inhibitory effects on protein, DNA, and RNA. The strong suppression of nucleic acids suggests interference with replication and transcription machinery, possibly through oxidative stress (hydrogen peroxide) or specific antibacterial peptides present in royal jelly, such as royalisin and defensin-1 (Kwakman and Zaat, 2012 and Mandal and Mandal, 2011). The drastic decline in RNA (up to 96% inhibition with black sativa honey) indicates disruption of ribosomal function and protein synthesis pathways. The differential responses between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria could be attributed to structural differences in their cell walls. Gram-negative *E. coli* has an outer membrane that may increase susceptibility to lipophilic compounds and phenolics, while Gram-positive *B. subtilis* may be more resilient, with some metabolic stimulation under certain conditions (Viuda-Martos *et al.*, 2008). Overall, these findings suggest that cotton honey exerts stronger inhibitory effects on nucleic acids, whereas black sativa honey can either inhibit or stimulate protein metabolism depending on bacterial type. This highlights the importance of honey's botanical origin in determining its antimicrobial potential.

The findings of this study demonstrate that bee royal jelly significantly alters the biochemical composition of both *B. subtilis* and *E. coli*, but with distinct patterns of activity. Royal jelly of cotton honey exhibited strong inhibitory effects on protein, DNA, and RNA synthesis in both bacteria, indicating potent antibacterial activity. In contrast, royal jelly of black sativa honey displayed a dual effect: it stimulated protein

synthesis in *B. subtilis* while inhibiting nucleic acid synthesis, and it strongly suppressed all macromolecules in *E. coli*. These results highlight that the antibacterial properties of bee royal jelly depend not only on bacterial type (Gram-positive vs. Gram-negative) but also on the botanical origin of the honey. The strong suppression of nucleic acid and protein synthesis suggests that royal jelly and its associated honey types could serve as effective natural antibacterial agents, offering potential applications in alternative medicine, food preservation, and the control of antibiotic-resistant pathogens. Future studies should focus on identifying the specific bioactive compounds responsible for these effects and exploring their mechanisms of action at the molecular level.

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